

Genetic Variability of Morphological Traits among Indian Mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.Czern & Coss) Genotypes under non- irrigated and irrigated condition

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Abstract

Water calamity results in the screening of drought tolerant genotypes which were suitable for both non-irrigated as well as in irrigated condition. Keeping consideration over this experiment was designed to study genetic variability and heritability under non- irrigated and irrigated condition on some morphological and quality traits an experiment on Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.Czern & Coss), was conducted by accommodating 20 genotypes, from various Rapeseed & Mustard centres located across country, randomly in three replications during Rabi 2016-17 in Randomized Complete Block Design (RBCD), one subjected to a drought regime inside the Rainout shelter under non-irrigated condition which was also devoid of rainfall and another one provided with normal irrigated field condition in Dr. Rajendra Prasad Central Agricultural University, Pusa, Samastipur. Analysis of variance for the studied traits revealed considerably exploitable variability. Out of 20 genotypes under both non-irrigated as well as irrigated condition, Rajendra Suphalam showed tolerance towards water stressed condition and performed well in terms of productivity in an irrigated situation for all the traits. PKRS-28 identified as tolerant genotype under non- irrigated, and Pusa Mahak as well suited under an irrigated condition in terms of flowering – maturity, siliqua characteristics and yield contributing traits. Under both conditions, high heritability coupled with high GAM for traits namely, HFPB and SBP¹ which were indicative of preponderance of additive gene action for expression of these traits hence are acquiescent for simple selection. The height of first primary branch and secondary branches per plant due to wide variability, meagre environmental influence along with high heritability and genetic advance suggested the exploitation of these traits for the further breeding programme as these traits are fixable in nature can be utilized in further segregating generations. The initiation of primary branches from the lowest position of the plant can accommodate number of branches and also provides a way to utilize the non- usable portion of the mustard plant from the base up to 55-60 cm.

Keywords: *Brassica juncea* L., Heritability, Genetic Advance, Non- Irrigated, Quality Traits

Introduction

Crop *Brassic*as played a vital role in national oilseed sector, greatly influencing the Indian Agricultural economy. Rapeseed mustard group of oleiferous *Brassic*as along with other cultivated rapeseed, namely toria and yellow sarson resulted in the transformation of Indian oilseed sector, achieving the goal of self - sufficiency called Yellow- Revolution.

The principle objective of mustard breeding programme aims at improvement in yield, reliability in performance, stability, and adaptation over a wide range of environments and quality. Grain yield is genetically established and depends on various other agro - morphological traits like primary and secondary branches, total siliqua/ plant, 1000 seed weight, harvest index, physiological properties like root and leaf parameters and quality viz. oil content that influence yield.

The success of plant breeding programs relies heavily on the existence of genetic variability in plants for particular traits. For successful utilization of genetic variability crop breeders emphatically search for the traits of importance and subsequently to incorporate it genetically into a usable variety. Moreover plant ideotype of *Brassic*a, possessing desirable component traits, contributing towards yield in a specified (here rainfed condition) environment could provide a basis for sustainable *Brassic*a improvement (Donald, 1962a&b). It can also provide a valuable guide to breeders particularly hybridization followed by pedigree selection for varietal development under rain-dependent/residual moisture critical environment.

Material and Methods

The experiment consisting of 20 Indian mustard genotypes was planted in October 2016 under two conditions, i.e., non-irrigated and irrigated (two irrigation) condition, laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications during *Rabi* season (2015-16), including check for variability and heritability study, received from different All India Co-ordinated Research Project- Rapeseed & Mustard centres: DRMR, Bharatpur, Rajasthan, CCSHAU, Hisar, Haryana, BARC, Trombay, Maharashtra, GBPUAT, Pantnagar, Uttarakhand, CSAUAT, Kanpur, U.P, IARI, New Delhi, ARS, RAU, Sriganaganagar, Rajasthan and DR.RPCA, Dholi, Bihar, providing only basal dose of fertilizers i.e. N:P₂O₅:K₂O:S:: 40:40:40:40 kg/ha under residual moisture conditions inside rainout shelter and 40 Basal dose of fertilizer N:20 P₂O₅:20 K₂O:40 S kg/ha and other at green siliqua stage (E₄, 65DAS) required 40 N for top dressing after pre-flowering stage at Research Farm of Dr. Rajendra Prasad Central Agricultural University Farm (25.29° N, 85.40° E and 51.80 m MSL), Pusa, Samastipur, Bihar. Keeping row to row and plant to plant distance 30cm and 10cm, respectively. The spacing between plants was maintained at 10cm by thinning at 14 DAS.

The observations were recorded for Grain Yield/Plot (kg/ha) (GY/P). The data were recorded on five randomly selected plants from each genotype in each replication leaving the border rows to avoid the sampling error. The observations were recorded using standard methodology. Readings from five plants were averaged replication-wise and the mean data subjected for analysis by using statistical package WINDOSTAT version 9.2 (INDOSTAT Service, Hyderabad) for yield and its morpho-physio-quality traits.

The phenotypic variance was partitioned into genotypic and environmental variances for a clear understanding of the pattern of variations. The GCV, PCV, heritability, genetic advance, GAM were calculated following standard statistical methods (Burton, 1952; Lush, 1949; Burton and Devane, 1953 and Johnson *et al.*, 1955).

Results and Discussion

On perusal of table 1 revealed that the genotypes exhibited highly significant differences among themselves for twenty four characters *viz.*, Days to first flower open, Days to physiological maturity, Days to cessation of flowering, Height of first primary branch, Primary branches per plant, Secondary branches per plant, Number of siliqua on Primary Mother Axis, Length of Primary Mother Axis, Number of seeds siliqua⁻¹, Taproot length, Root volume, Root mass, Specific leaf weight, Leaf membrane stability index, Relative water content, Excised leaf water loss, Catalase activity, Peroxidase activity, Biological yield, Harvest index, Dry matter efficiency, Grain yield ha⁻¹ and Oil yield ha⁻¹ except for Siliqua density, Length of siliqua, Relative growth rate, Leaf area index, Chlorophyll content, Drought tolerance index, Stress intensity, Proline accumulation, 1000 seed weight and Oil content under four environment E₁ and E₄ indicated the genetic worth of the studied materials. Various scientists have reported significant variability for yield and its components: morphological, physiological and quality (Singh *et al.*, 2009; Vijayakumar *et al.*, 2001 and Misra 2012).

Based on mean performance table 2, all the characters have mean values less in non-irrigated condition than in irrigated condition mainly due to stress condition provided during avoidance of adequate water supply in the form of rainfall as well as irrigation water. In the absence of water, plant completed its vegetative phase as soon as possible in order to reach the reproductive phase to complete its life cycle. The plant along with completion of its life cycle also synthesizes oil side by side which is less as compared to the irrigated condition. The lack of water affects flowering, the total number of siliqua, 1000 seed weight as well as partitioning of DME. Under both conditions, Rajendra Suphlam is well acquainted and adaptive genotype which showed superiority for all traits under residual moisture & irrigated condition. PKRS-28 identified as tolerant genotype under non-irrigated and Pusa Mahak as well suited under an irrigated condition in terms of high yield and productivity with flowering – maturity, siliqua, and yield contributing traits.

Characters, with a wide range of variability, HFPB, SBP⁻¹ and SD were influenced by both macro and microenvironmental conditions, while other characters have less under range showed in (table 3) under both non-irrigated and irrigated condition.

The genotypic coefficient of variation estimates had close agreement with phenotypic coefficient of variation estimates (Table 4) for characters Days to first flower open, Days to physiological maturity, Days to cessation of flowering, Height of first primary branch, Primary branches per plant, Secondary branches per plant, Number of siliqua on Primary Mother Axis, Length of Primary Mother Axis, Siliqua density, Length of siliqua, Number of seeds siliqua⁻¹, Taproot length, Root volume, Root mass, Relative growth rate, Leaf area index, Specific leaf weight, Chlorophyll content, Leaf membrane stability index, Relative water content, Excised leaf water loss, Catalase activity, Peroxidase activity, Proline accumulation and Oil content indicated that influence of environment over these traits are meager except environmental effects are much more influenced for Drought tolerance index, Stress intensity, Biological yield, Harvest index, Dry matter efficiency, Grain yield ha⁻¹ and Oil yield ha⁻¹ which showed large difference under both conditions. Similar findings were in accordance with Meena *et al.*, 2014.

High heritability coupled with high genetic advance was observed for Days first to flower open, Height of first primary branch, Primary branches per plant, Secondary branches per plant, Number of siliqua on Primary Mother Axis under both the condition indicated that greater contribution of the additive genetic component. Therefore, suggested exercising individual plant selection in an early segregating generation for exploitation of fixable genetic variance. These results were in accordance with Synrem *et al.*, 2014; Ejaz-Ul-Hasan *et al.*, 2015.

Conclusion

From the above findings and discussion conclusion drawn that for the height of first primary branch and secondary branches per plant there is the presence of wide variability along with high heritability and genetic advance suggested the exploitation of these traits for the further breeding programme as these traits are fixable in nature can be utilized in further segregating generations. The environmental influence over these two characters is also meager in nature. The initiation of primary branches from the lowest position of the plant can accommodate number of branches and also provides a way to utilize the non- usable portion of the mustard plant from the base up to 55-60 cm.

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Table 1. Analysis of variance for morphological and quality characters in Indian mustard.

Source of Variation	Environments	D.F.	Mean squares										
			DFFO	DPM	DCF	HFPB	PBP ⁻¹	SBP ⁻¹	SPMA	LPMA	SD	LS	SS ⁻¹
Replication	E ₁	2	0.217	1.317	10.517**	5.357**	0.229	0.581	1.233	23.401**	0.009	0.024	0.226
	E ₄	2	1.550	15.350**	5.400**	10.181**	0.098	1.219	1.028	10.523**	0.005	0.017	0.220
Genotype	E ₁	19	58.825**	16.000**	17.904**	552.377**	1.907*	53.884**	125.323**	117.265**	0.634	0.934	2.955**
	E ₄	19	39.891**	24.530**	33.154**	800.076	3.967**	48.113**	112.141**	182.315**	0.103	0.753	4.071**
Error	E ₁	38	1.901	4.387	4.604	5.817	0.238	0.185	1.255	7.796	0.003	0.023	0.135
	E ₄	38	1.041	9.701	11.154	4.922	0.120	0.489	0.782	5.585	0.003	0.041	0.209

Source of Variation	Environments	D.F.	Mean squares					
			TSW	BY	HI	DME	OC	Grain yield ha ⁻¹
Replication	E ₁	2	0.07	15690.42**	6.71**	5.95**	0.39	278.26**
	E ₄	2	0.16	177298.06**	6.25**	2.95	0.48	28273.82**
Genotype	E ₁	19	0.73	132769.19**	29.43**	21.52**	0.38	85216.37**
	E ₄	19	1.81	353907.72**	30.44**	19.81**	0.76	188327.55**
Error	E ₁	38	0.04	42472.87	6.71	4.46	0.44	26870.36
	E ₄	38	0.48	53620.88	6.52	4.68	0.43	59077.45

Table 2: Mean performance standard error (mean), critical difference for morphological and quality characters in Indian mustard.

Characters Varieties	DFFO		DPM		DCF		HFPPB	
	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄
DRMRLEJ902	38.67	40.70	120.00	124.30	98.33	95.00	51.37	35.50
DRMR150-35	43.00	45.00	121.70	124.30	95.33	100.00	42.38	49.50
NRCDR2	44.67	39.00	119.30	122.30	93.67	99.00	49.91	47.10
RH8814	41.33	41.30	118.70	122.30	91.00	99.00	55.50	48.90
TM151	49.00	50.30	120.00	123.30	90.67	95.67	62.05	43.90
TM128	51.00	49.00	120.70	123.70	92.33	94.33	65.09	38.50
KRANTI	40.67	45.00	119.00	119.70	92.67	96.33	55.45	77.20
KMR10-1	44.00	47.00	119.30	122.30	93.67	94.67	46.03	42.70
MAYA	42.00	40.30	118.70	122.00	96.00	99.00	54.78	65.00
ROHINI	53.67	42.00	121.70	121.70	95.67	94.33	65.91	68.40
PKRS28	46.67	47.30	120.30	120.00	92.33	102.00	26.06	25.30
PUSA MUSTARD 25	50.33	46.00	118.30	121.70	92.67	103.00	52.50	45.70
PUSA MUSTARD 28(NPJ-124)	47.33	49.00	118.70	121.70	92.33	102.30	28.83	22.00
RGN-13	49.00	51.70	118.70	119.70	92.00	100.70	25.34	23.90
RAURD 212	45.00	45.00	121.00	121.70	95.67	96.67	42.09	46.00
RAURD 78	49.67	50.30	120.70	121.70	90.00	100.00	46.56	38.50
VARUNA(CHECK)	45.67	46.30	129.00	133.00	94.67	101.00	27.86	28.00
PUSA BOLD(CHECK)	43.67	45.00	120.70	124.30	92.67	100.30	54.09	56.50
PUSA MAHAK(JD-6) (CHECK)	41.33	43.30	121.30	125.70	95.00	101.70	46.85	65.80
RAJENDRA SUFLAM(CHECK)	36.67	42.30	119.00	122.70	87.67	91.00	21.64	19.50
SEm (±)	0.8	0.59	1.21	1.8	1.24	1.93	1.39	1.28
CD (5%)	2.28	1.69	3.46	5.15	3.54	5.52	3.98	3.67
CD (1%)	3.05	2.26	4.63	6.9	4.75	7.39	5.33	4.91
	PBP⁻¹		SBP⁻¹		SPMA		LPMA	

Characters Varieties	E ₁		E ₄		E ₁		E ₄		E ₁		E ₄	
DRMRLEJ902	3.73	5.00	5.47	10.87	40.13	60.60	59.35	68.50				
DRMR150-35	3.67	4.93	9.00	9.40	42.13	55.47	65.30	58.50				
NRCDR2	3.07	4.53	7.00	9.53	38.80	46.47	58.23	56.10				
RH8814	3.93	4.07	7.53	8.00	36.00	50.33	60.53	61.90				
TM151	4.03	4.00	6.07	6.20	40.33	62.13	62.43	46.80				
TM128	4.07	4.00	9.60	7.00	55.07	59.40	55.39	56.40				
KRANTI	3.27	4.07	9.53	8.60	42.87	51.40	50.22	43.50				
KMR10-1	3.20	4.13	5.53	8.53	38.73	44.47	55.61	67.20				
MAYA	4.13	4.13	10.07	9.07	40.87	57.20	52.67	53.70				
ROHINI	4.47	4.60	15.53	15.67	48.00	62.47	54.61	53.80				
PKRS28	4.93	4.87	21.33	17.75	50.07	53.20	64.93	53.40				
PUSA MUSTARD 25	4.97	4.13	12.53	11.00	49.40	51.60	61.10	56.20				
PUSA MUSTARD 28(NPJ-124)	4.80	4.53	17.00	11.07	43.47	57.27	62.68	48.50				
RGN-13	4.07	4.47	12.60	12.53	48.67	46.07	63.11	50.00				
RAURD 212	4.80	4.33	9.07	9.53	47.47	53.60	53.09	53.80				
RAURD 78	4.53	4.53	11.00	15.07	53.40	56.53	51.21	57.20				
VARUNA(CHECK)	4.47	7.53	12.13	15.60	45.60	48.53	60.77	61.70				
PUSA BOLD	3.47	3.93	14.87	14.07	48.53	53.47	69.13	45.20				
PUSA MAHAK(JD-6)	5.13	3.93	10.47	18.13	52.60	51.40	69.67	65.10				
RAJENDRA SUFLAM	6.40	8.27	16.60	20.07	61.40	68.17	71.89	71.80				
SEm (±)	0.28	0.20	0.25	0.40	0.65	0.51	1.61	1.36				
CD (5%)	0.81	0.57	0.71	1.16	1.85	1.46	4.62	3.91				
CD (1%)	1.08	0.77	0.95	1.55	2.48	1.96	6.18	5.23				

Varieties	SD		LS		SS ⁻¹		TSW		BY	
	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄
DRMRLEJ902	0.81	0.90	5.22	4.90	11.53	11.70	4.78	5.63	1138.33	1610.00
DRMR150-35	0.87	1.00	4.26	4.70	12.33	11.70	5.11	5.70	1273.33	1973.33
NRCDR2	1.08	0.80	5.35	4.00	12.64	9.33	4.34	4.74	1183.33	2016.67
RH8814	0.89	0.80	5.19	5.00	12.73	12.10	5.07	5.62	1196.67	1923.33
TM151	0.95	1.30	5.17	4.70	12.67	9.73	4.36	5.59	1140.00	2016.00
TM128	1.22	1.10	5.19	4.00	13.30	10.70	5.47	5.25	1026.67	2243.33
KRANTI	0.86	1.20	5.26	5.10	11.40	11.70	4.82	4.89	1380.00	2183.33
KMR10-1	0.70	0.70	5.45	4.60	14.40	12.90	5.26	5.58	910.00	1473.33
MAYA	2.85	1.10	5.61	5.60	14.47	9.53	5.23	4.80	1053.33	2423.33
ROHINI	0.94	1.20	3.99	5.20	11.60	13.90	5.25	3.97	1733.33	2226.67
PKRS28	0.97	1.00	5.67	4.10	11.67	11.50	4.73	5.64	1376.67	1896.67
PUSA MUSTARD 25	0.81	0.90	6.22	4.70	11.47	10.70	5.02	3.75	1085.00	1443.33
PUSA MUSTARD 28(NPJ-124)	0.83	1.20	5.74	5.00	11.20	11.90	4.76	5.19	1348.33	1590.00
RGN-13	0.77	0.90	5.77	4.90	12.67	11.70	4.43	3.63	850.00	1643.33
RAURD 212	1.10	1.00	5.18	4.80	11.47	11.70	5.43	5.45	1403.33	1540.00
RAURD 78	1.17	1.00	4.38	4.40	11.93	10.50	5.42	5.54	1103.33	1583.33
VARUNA(CHECK)	0.75	0.80	5.11	5.00	11.13	11.50	4.39	5.58	980.00	1440.00
PUSA BOLD	0.74	1.20	5.35	4.90	12.60	10.50	4.60	6.06	1006.67	1540.00
PUSA MAHAK(JD-6)	0.76	1.00	5.41	4.40	11.47	10.50	5.28	6.41	1250.00	1506.67
RAJENDRA SUFLAM	1.04	1.40	6.11	6.00	13.23	13.00	6.37	6.36	1420.00	2486.67
SEm (±)	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.51	0.21	0.26	0.12	0.40	118.99	133.69
CD (5%)	0.09	0.09	0.25	1.46	0.61	108.80	0.34	1.15	340.65	382.75
CD (1%)	0.12	0.11	0.34	1.96	0.81	145.70	0.45	1.53	456.27	512.67

Varieties	Harvest index		Dry matter efficiency		Oil content		Grain yield ha ⁻¹	
	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄
DRMRLEJ902	16.69	22.10	13.92	17.70	38.93	36.90	1055.45	1944.30
DRMR150-35	16.23	18.40	13.38	14.80	39.19	38.70	1111.00	1999.80
NRCDR2	21.28	19.00	17.83	15.50	38.63	38.40	1390.60	2129.40
RH8814	18.43	24.40	15.53	20.00	38.82	38.40	1203.58	2592.30
TM151	19.73	19.00	16.43	15.40	40.04	38.80	1259.13	2092.40
TM128	23.97	15.10	19.89	12.20	39.21	38.50	1370.23	1870.20
KRANTI	18.32	16.90	15.37	14.10	39.34	39.20	1388.75	2055.40
KMR10-1	26.60	27.90	22.27	22.80	39.25	38.60	1333.20	2259.00
MAYA	20.89	14.90	17.59	12.30	38.95	38.30	1203.58	1999.80
ROHINI	15.25	20.60	12.53	17.00	39.15	39.20	1462.82	2527.50
PKRS28	16.55	19.30	13.76	16.10	39.10	38.50	1259.13	2036.80
PUSA MUSTARD 25	18.79	24.00	15.87	19.70	39.32	38.80	1129.52	1907.20
PUSA MUSTARD 28(NPJ-124)	19.65	22.40	16.56	18.40	38.98	39.00	1425.79	1972.00
RGN-13	23.50	21.30	19.79	17.80	38.67	38.40	1092.48	1944.30
RAURD 212	14.74	21.60	12.17	17.80	39.07	38.30	1129.52	1833.20
RAURD 78	22.61	22.40	18.76	18.40	39.33	38.50	1351.72	1962.80
VARUNA(CHECK)	19.73	23.50	15.28	17.70	38.49	38.40	1055.45	1870.20
PUSA BOLD(CHECK)	16.71	19.70	13.86	15.90	39.01	38.40	925.83	1638.70
PUSA MAHAK(JD-6) (CHECK)	17.12	22.20	14.11	17.70	39.02	38.00	1185.07	1851.70
RAJENDRA SUFLAM(CHECK)	20.46	18.50	17.19	15.10	38.45	37.80	1610.95	2536.80
SEm (±)	1.50	1.47	1.22	1.25	0.38	0.38	94.64	140.33
CD (5%)	4.28	4.22	3.49	3.58	1.10	1.08	270.95	401.75
CD (1%)	5.74	5.65	4.68	4.79	1.47	1.44	362.92	538.12

Table 3: General Mean, CV, and Range of morphological and quality characters in Indian mustard.

	Characters	MEAN		RANGE		CV%	
		E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄
1	Days to first flower open	45.16	45.30	36.66-53.66	39.00-51.67	3.05	2.25
2	Days to physiological maturity	120.33	122.90	118.33-129.00	119.67-133.00	1.84	2.53
3	Days to cessation of flowering	93.21	98.30	87.66-98.33	91.00-103.00	2.30	3.40
4	Height of first primary branch	46.01	44.40	21.63-65.91	19.51-77.16	5.24	5.00
5	Primary branches per plant	4.25	4.70	3.06-4.60	3.93-8.27	11.46	7.36
6	Secondary branches per plant	11.14	11.88	5.46-21.33	6.20-20.07	3.86	5.89
7	Number of siliqua on Primary Mother Axis	46.17	54.49	36.00-61.40	44.47-68.17	2.43	1.62
8	Length of Primary Mother Axis	60.09	56.46	50.22-71.88	43.48-71.77	4.65	4.19
9	Siliqua density	1.00	1.01	0.70-2.85	0.66-1.40	5.36	5.08
10	Length of siliqua	5.28	4.80	3.99-6.21	3.95-6.00	2.89	4.22
11	Number of seeds siliqua ⁻¹	12.29	11.34	11.13-14.46	9.33-13.87	2.98	4.03
12	1000 seed weight	5.00	5.27	4.34-6.37	3.63-6.41	4.06	13.15
13	Biological yield	1192.91	1837.97	850-1733.33	1440.00-2486.67	17.28	12.60
14	Harvest index	19.36	20.65	14.73-26.60	14.92-27.85	13.38	12.37
15	Dry matter efficiency	16.10	16.81	12.16-22.27	12.20-22.80	13.11	12.87
16	Oil content	39.04	38.45	38.44-40.03	36.90-39.19	1.70	1.70
17	Grain yieldha ⁻¹	1247.19	2051.18	925.83-1610-95	1638.73-2592.33	13.14	11.85

Table 4: Genotypic and phenotypic variance and coefficient of variation, heritability in a broad sense and genetic advance as percent of mean for morpho-quality characters in Indian mustard.

S.NO.	Character	Genotypic variance		Phenotypic variance	
		E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄
1	Days to first flower open	18.97	12.95	20.88	13.99
2	Days to physiological maturity	3.87	4.94	8.26	14.64
3	Days to the cessation of flowering	4.43	7.33	9.04	18.49
4	The height of first primary branch	182.19	265.05	188.00	269.97
5	Primary branches per plant	0.56	1.28	0.79	1.40
6	Secondary branches per plant	17.90	15.87	18.08	16.36
7	Number of siliqua on Primary Mother Axis	41.36	37.12	42.61	37.90
8	Length of Primary Mother Axis	36.49	58.91	44.29	64.50
9	Siliqua density	0.210	0.03	0.213	0.04
10	Length of siliqua	0.30	0.24	0.33	0.28
11	Number of seeds siliqua ⁻¹	0.94	1.29	1.07	1.50
12	1000 seed weight	0.23	0.44	0.27	0.92
13	Biological yield	30098.77	100095.62	72571.65	153716.48
14	Harvest index	7.57	7.97	41.28	14.49
15	Dry matter efficiency	5.69	5.04	10.15	9.72
16	Oil content	0.12	0.11	0.42	0.54
17	Grain yieldha ⁻¹	19448.67	43083.37	46319.03	102160.81
S.NO.	Character	GCV		PCV	
		E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄
1	Days to first flower open	9.64	7.94	10.12	8.26
2	Days to physiological maturity	1.64	1.81	2.39	3.11
3	Days to the cessation of flowering	2.26	2.75	3.23	4.37
4	The height of first primary branch	29.33	36.67	29.80	37.01
5	Primary branches per plant	17.52	24.09	20.94	25.19
6	Secondary branches per plant	37.96	33.53	38.15	34.04
7	Number of siliqua on Primary Mother Axis	13.93	11.18	14.14	11.30
8	Length of Primary Mother Axis	10.05	13.59	11.07	14.22
9	Siliqua density	45.60	17.99	45.91	18.69
10	Length of siliqua	10.43	10.14	10.82	10.98
11	Number of seeds siliqua ⁻¹	7.89	10.00	8.43	10.79
12	1000 seed weight	9.60	12.61	10.42	18.22
13	Biological yield	14.54	17.21	22.58	21.33
14	Harvest index	14.21	13.67	19.52	18.44
15	Dry matter efficiency	14.81	13.36	19.78	18.55
16	Oil content	0.37	0.86	1.66	1.90
17	Grain yieldha ⁻¹	11.18	10.12	17.26	15.58

S.NO.	Character	Heritability		GAM (%)	
		E ₁	E ₄	E ₁	E ₄
1	Days to first flower open	90.85	92.57	18.94	15.74
2	Days to physiological maturity	46.85	33.74	2.31	2.17
3	Days to the cessation of flowering	49.00	39.64	3.26	3.57
4	The height of first primary branch	96.91	98.18	59.49	74.85
5	Primary branches per plant	70.89	91.43	30.21	47.47
6	Secondary branches per plant	99.00	97.00	77.79	68.02
7	Number of siliqua on Primary Mother Axis	97.07	97.94	28.26	22.79
8	Length of Primary Mother Axis	82.39	91.33	18.80	26.77
9	Siliqua density	98.59	75.00	93.30	35.66
10	Length of siliqua	90.91	85.71	20.70	19.28
11	Number of seeds siliqua ⁻¹	87.85	86.00	15.19	19.11
12	1000 seed weight	85.19	47.83	18.20	17.98
13	Biological yield	41.47	65.12	19.29	28.61
14	Harvest index	18.34	55.00	21.31	20.89
15	Dry matter efficiency	56.06	51.85	22.84	19.81
16	Oil content	28.58	20.37	0.17	0.81
17	Grain yieldha ⁻¹	41.99	42.17	14.93	13.54